

Radiotherapy treatment planning with preemptive boost method.

Preliminary results

Jeno Palvolgyi

Abstract

Aim

With the traditional treatment planning method, the dose distribution of the boosted high risk region contributes to the dose to the low risk region resulting excess dose to the organs at risk. The aim of the study was to reduce the excess dose.

Materials and Methods

With the presented treatment planning method, the dose contribution of the high risk region to the low risk is preemptively is taken into account. The method was tested with VMAT radiotherapy treatment plans of 12 head&neck and 10 bladder cancer patients. The average dose to the targets and organs at risk obtained with the traditional and the preemptive planning method was compared.

Results

The excess dose reduction effect in the preemptive treatment planning was found relative low in head&neck patients, while it was more effective in bladder cases.

Introduction

With the traditional treatment planning process, in the first step the dose planning for the low risk and the high risk target regions with the low risk dose prescription is performed, In the second step, the boost dose is planned and added to the base plan. While the boost dose distribution contributes to the dose distribution being at the low risk region and being at the organs at risk (OAR) surrounding the boost region, resulting in an elevated dose compared to the prescribed one. The aim of the study was to reduce the excess dose at the OARs and at the low risk regions.

Materials and Methods

The preemptive radiotherapy planning concept

To obtain the goal, we reversed the order in the treatment planning process as follows. In the first step, we performed the boost planning for the high risk region as a base plane. In the second step, the composite dose to the low risk region regions was planned with the base plan's bias dose. The dose distribution has the difference to one planned with the traditional method that the dose contribution of the boost to the low risk region and to the surrounding OAR regions is included.

We tested the method with 12 head&neck and with 10 bladder cancer cases preparing traditional and preemptive radiotherapy treatment plans with the Monaco v5.11 treatment planning system. 6MV VMAT irradiation technique was used. Typical coronal treatment plan views are illustrated in Fig. 1. and 2. The dose prescription for the head and neck patients was: 54Gy and 60 Gy delivered simultan with 30 fractions to the low and medium risk regions, while the boost dose was 10Gy per 5 fractions to the high risk region, The prescription dose for the bladder cancer patients was: 44Gy to the low risk region and 20Gy boost both per 2Gy fractions. Typical dose volume histograms of the two plan versions are illustrated in Fig. 3 and 4.

We collected the average dose values to PTVboost, to the medium minus high risk region (PTV60-), to the low minus medium risk (PTV54-) or low minus high risk regions PTV44-) and to the organs at risks. We computed the difference between the corresponding values obtained with the preemptive and traditional treatment planning methods (PREE-TRAD) summarized in Table 1. and 2. We also counted the number of PREE-TRAD values being lower than 0.5 Gy (lower) and once being larger than 0.5 Gy (larger).

Fig.1. Coronal view of the composite dose distribution of one of the head&neck cancer cases

Fig.2. Coronal view of the composite dose distribution of one of the bladder cancer cases

Fig.3. The Dose volume histograms of one of the head & neck patients obtained with the traditional (TRAD) and preemptive (PREE) planning method

Fig.4. The Dose volume histograms of one of the bladder cancer patients obtained with the traditional (TRAD) and preemptive (PREE) planning method

	PTV60-			PTV54-			SpinalCord_PRV			Parotid_Left			Parotid_Right			Mandible			Oral_Cavity			BrainStem_PRV			Esophagus_Up			Larynx		
	TRAD	FREE	FREE-TRAI	TRAD	FREE	FREE-TRAI	TRAD	FREE	FREE-TRAI	TRAD	FREE	FREE-TRAI	TRAD	FREE	FREE-TRAI	TRAD	FREE	FREE-TRAI	TRAD	FREE	FREE-TRAI	TRAD	FREE	FREE-TRAI	TRAD	FREE	FREE-TRAI	TRAD	FREE	FREE-TRAI
1	6476	6330	-146	5750	5667	-83	1502	1466	-36	1672	1407	-265	2658	2452	-206	5740	5516	-224	6146	5950	-196	793	705	-88	3886	3670	-216	4289	4169	-120
2	6422	6528	106	5731	5812	81	2202	2285	83	3282	3382	100	3749	3240	-509	5375	5388	13	6093	6115	22	2447	2200	-247	4106	4172	66	6602	6783	181
3	6367	6276	-91	5687	5669	-18	2747	2711	-36	2109	2374	265	1640	1593	-57	3082	3038	-44	3442	3149	-293	473	392	-81	5828	5937	109			
4	6321	6339	18	5797	5785	-12	1813	2202	389	4381	4454	73	3331	3249	-82	4890	4967	77	6344	6104	-240	791	809	18	4101	4271	170	6493	6210	-283
5	6276	6353	77	5673	5630	-43	892	1156	264	2849	2959	110	2560	2597	37	4357	4343	-14	4887	4902	15	1588	1433	-155	4654	5042	388			
6	6432	6240	-192	5718	5656	-62	1609	1918	309	2260	1985	-275	2190	2162	-28	5502	5267	-235				1358	1366	8	1794	1904	110	5312	5054	-254
7	6356	6342	-14	5691	5619	-72	1159	1274	15	2345	2105	-240	2025	1957	-68	4366	4223	-143	2777	2636	-141	219	218	1	1713	1643	-70	5578	5400	-178
8	6331	6416	85	5722	5684	-38	1414	1657	243	3066	2997	-69	5038	4857	-181	4559	4544	-15	6474	6404	-70	831	862	-169	4136	2232	-1904	4350	3684	-666
9	6444	6478	34	5850	5747	-3	2962	2969	7	2711	2459	-252	2953	2828	-125	4715	4429	-286	5247	5098	-149	1084	988	-94	2136	2231	95	6803	6872	69
10	6318	6361	43	5729	5715	-14	2031	2705	674	2834	2703	-131	4768	4841	73	6062	5987	-75	6544	6757	213	1422	1418	-4	6063	4556	-1507	4905	3673	-1232
11	6460	6291	-173	5742	5721	-21	1648	1182	-466	2795	2943	309	2315	2199	-116	3663	3483	-180	5486	4859	-627	804	739	-65	4820	4399	-421	6721	6752	31
12	6444	6408	-36	5737	5714	-25	1736	1554	-182	2166	2030	-136	2805	2709	-96	4799	4758	-41	6130	5989	-141	460	519	59	4877	4758	-119	6815	6774	-41
average	6387,25	6363,5	-24,1	5735,6	5701,6	-25,8	1809,58	1923,25	105,33			-42,6	3002,7		-113,2	4755,55	4661,92	-97,25	5415,5	5269,4	-146,1	1073,64	954,08	-68,08	3930,6	3734,6	-274,9	5786,8	5537,1	-272,4
scatter	66,7	82,8	103,9	48,6	59,2	42,1	602,87	640,30	294,91			208,62	1054,26		148,01	893,32	845,87	113,74	1262,07	1328,78	212,88	611,10	558,36	90,06	1448,82	1396,46	703,83	1026,33	1326,05	436,3
lower			4			3			2			6			9			6			8			7			6			6
higher			3			1			6			5			1			1			1			1			6			2

Table 1. The average dose values in cGy in head&neck cancer cases

	PTVboost			PTVv44-			Bowel_small			fem_Left			fem-Right			Rectum		
	TRAD	FREE	FREE-TRAD	TRAD	FREE	FREE-TRAD	TRAD	FREE	FREE-TRAD	TRAD	FREE	FREE-TRAD	TRAD	FREE	FREE-TRAD	TRAD	FREE	FREE-TRAD
1	65,1	65,7	0,6	50,9	48,7	-2,2	3,2	2,4	-0,8	26	19,5	-6,5	24,5	19,5	-5	30,8	29,2	1,6
2	65,1	66,2	1,1	49,4	47,3	-2,1	15,8	9,6	-6,2	25,5	18,3	-7,2	25,9	18,5	-7,4	30,2	29,5	0,7
3	65,8	65,6	-0,2	49,6	46,9	-2,7	18,5	13,7	-4,8	23,2	20,6	-2,6	24	19,9	-4,1	26,8	28,4	-2,4
4	65,5	65,5	0,0	49,2	49,2	0	20,3	14,8	-5,5	24	19,3	-4,7	26,6	19,4	-6,9	27,7	23,7	4
5	65,6	65,2	-0,4	45,9	46,4	-0,5	25,8	30,1	4,3	30,3	21,5	-8,2	33,5	25,7	-7,8	19	24,3	-5,3
6	65	66,5	0,5	49,3	47,1	-2,2	19,3	15,5	-3,8	19,3	19,3	0	26,3	20,5	-5,8	24,9	22,7	2,2
7	65,3	66,1	1,2	49,5	49	-0,5	13,3	16,4	3,1	20,9	13,1	-7,8	17,6	14	-3,6	26	22,5	3,5
8	65,1	66,5	0,4	50,4	47,5	-2,9	16,8	15	-1,8	23,6	19,8	-3,8	26,1	19,2	-6,9	30,6	37,6	-7
9	65,9	65,7	-0,2	52,6	49,2	-2,4	3,4	2,7	-0,7	19,8	17,5	-2,3	21,5	18,3	-3,2	22,3	18,9	3,3
10	64,8	65,9	1,1	45,7	48	2,3	18,5	19,8	1,3	27,4	19,6	-7,8	25,2	19,4	-4,8	20,2	17,6	2,6
average	65,32	65,89	0,41	49,25	47,93	-1,32	15,49	14	-1,49	24	18,85	-5,09	25,12	19,44	-5,55	25,85	25,44	0,32
scatter	0,36	0,43	0,60	2,09	1,03	1,63	7,19	8,06	3,62	3,46	2,30	2,84	4,04	2,84	1,65	4,25	5,89	3,88
lower								9		7				9		10		3
higher						0		0		3			0		0			7

Table2. The average dose values in Gy in bladder cancer cases

Results

The average PREE-TRAD values and the effect of the preemptive treatment planning in the head&neck cancer cases:

medium-high risk region (PTV66-): no significant change

low-medium risk region (PTV54-): (0.25±0.4 Gy) slight decrease in the majority of cases

SpinalCord_PRV : (1 ±2.9Gy) increase in the majority of cases

Parotids : (0.4 to 1.1±1.4Gy) decrease in the majority of cases

Mandible : (0.9 ±1.1Gy) decrease in 50% of cases

Oral_cavity : (1.4 ±2.1Gy) decrease in the majority of cases

BrainStem : (0,6 ±0,9Gy) decrease in the majority of cases

Esophagus : various values

Larynx : various values, the Larynx was medium risk target area in 50% of cases

The average PREE-TRAD values given in bladder cancer cases:

low-high risk region (PTV44-) : (1.3±1.6Gy) decrease in 90% of patients

BowelSmall : (1.5±3.6Gy) decrease in 70% of patients

Femurs : (5.1±3.6Gy) decrease in 90% of patients

Rectum : (0,3±3,9Gy) increase in 70% of patients, various values

Discussion and Conclusion

In this study, we examined in dosimetric point of view the possibility to reduce the excess dose being out of the high risk region. The head&neck patients' stage was T4. The diagnosis was heterogeneous: mesopharynx, hypopharynx, tongue base and oral cavity. The boost dose prescription of 10Gy was low compared to the total dose of 70Gy. The preemptive planning resulted in an average reduction of 0.2-1.5Gy in PREE-TRAD values at the organs at risk except the SpinalCord_PRV, where we experienced higher dose values in 50% of cases. No significant change was observed at PTV60- and small one was at PTV54-.

The average PREE-TRAD values in the bladder cancer cases showed larger effect due to the more simple anatomical structures compared to the head&neck patients and due to the higher (20Gy) boost dose prescription, The preemptive planning's dose reduction effect was efficient in each bladder cancer cases at the low risk region and at the majority of organs at risk except the Rectum. The average PREE-TRAD values varied between 1.3 and 5.5Gy, while the dose values to the

Rectum showed various values.

Our preliminary results with low number of patients showed that the preemptive treatment planning method reduced the boost dose contribution at the majority of the organs surrounding the high risk region and could offer better quality therapy plans compared to the traditional one.